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RESETTLE Trial: Statistical Analysis Plan for Brain MRI Outcomes

Note: The primary Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) for the RESETTLE trial is registered on ClinicalTrials.gov (Study Plan section). The present document is a supplementary analysis plan pertaining exclusively to brain MRI outcomes and is archived on Zenodo.

Protocol title

Young adults with early-onset obesity treated with semaglutide – The RESETTLE study

Trial registration: EudraCT Number: 2019-002274-31, ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT05574439

Data collection: 24 January 2023 to 9 October 2025.

Version: 1.0

Abbreviations: ACC: anterior cingulate cortex; ALFF: amplitude of low-frequency fluctuations; BA: Brodmann area; dlPFC: dorsolateral prefrontal cortex; DXA: dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry; fALFF: fractional ALFF; HOMA-IR: Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance; ICA: independent component analysis; NAcc: nucleus accumbens; OFC: orbitofrontal cortex; PFC: prefrontal cortex; TFEQ: Three-Factor Eating Questionnaire; VAS: visual analogue scale; vmPFC: ventromedial prefrontal cortex.

Primary Outcome

Objective: Investigate the effect of semaglutide treatment on meal signaling between the hypothalamus and key brain regions associated with eating regulation.

Outcome: Functional connectivity between the hypothalamus and the right OFC/vmPFC assessed before and after a standardized meal.

Endpoint: The treatment-by-time interaction in the functional connectivity outcome from baseline (week 0) to end of treatment (week 68).

Additional sensitivity analyses with adjustment for weight change.

Secondary Outcomes

Outcomes will be assessed at baseline (cross-sectional associations) and for longitudinal modulation by treatment:

- **Appetite Network connectivity:** Functional connectivity within the Appetite Network, defined as hypothalamus, striatum (NAcc, caudate, putamen), insula/operculum, OFC, dlPFC, ACC, amygdala, and hippocampus. To avoid overlap with the primary outcome, voxels within the primary ROI mask (right OFC/vmPFC) will be excluded from seed-based secondary analyses using the hypothalamus as seed.
- **Structural brain measures:** Including gray matter volume, cortical thickness, and brain age.
- **Neural correlates of body weight, appetite (VAS), food preferences (Leeds Food Preference Questionnaire), and eating behavior (TFEQ).** This includes functional connectivity, data-driven approaches (e.g. ICA), and regional activity (ALFF/fALFF). Evaluation includes task-based activation during a food cue paradigm.
- **Association of biochemical markers (e.g., HOMA-IR, metabolic syndrome z-score) and anthropometrics (including DXA-derived fat percentage and fat-free mass) and socioeconomic factors with brain imaging outcomes.**

Analyses will be adjusted for sex and, where relevant, age, except for BrainAge analyses. Functional analyses will additionally be adjusted for individual fasting duration and time from meal ingestion to postprandial scan acquisition. Supplementary analyses will include sex-stratified analyses and analyses restricted to the semaglutide treatment group.

Multiple Comparisons

The primary outcome constitutes a single pre-specified test ($p < 0.05$). Pre-specified secondary outcomes are reported with effect sizes and interpreted in the context of existing literature.